

Sparse Dynamic Programming for Longest Common Substring

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Abstract

We present a simple algorithm for solving the longest common substring problem. Let x and y be two strings, of length n and m respectively. Let $k \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$ be an additional parameter. Let $x^{(k)} := (x[1..k], \dots, x[n-k+1..n])$, with $y^{(k)}$ being defined analogously. Finally, let $\lambda_k(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)})$ denote the number of pairs $(i, j) \in \{1, \dots, n-k+1\} \times \{1, \dots, m-k+1\}$ such that $x^{(k)}[i] = y^{(k)}[j]$. Our algorithm requires $O(k^2(n+m) + \lambda_k(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}))$ expected (only due to hashmap lookups/insertions) amortized time and $O(k(n+m))$ space. If x and y share a substring of length at least k , then it requires $\Theta(k(n+m-k) + \lambda_k(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}))$ expected amortized time and $\Theta(k(n+m-k))$ space. In this case, the use of bit-packing (if feasible) allows to further reduce complexities to $\Theta(n+m-k + \lambda_k(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}))$ and $\Theta(n+m-k)$, respectively. We also consider an i.i.d. model. Here, by appropriately choosing the value of k (such that $k \in O(\log(nm))$), we achieve (abusing notation) $\mathbb{E}[\lambda_k(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)})] \leq n+m$.

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0 Notations and Assumptions

0.1 General Notations

For all $a \in \mathbb{N}$, we define $\mathbb{N}_{\geq a} := \{b \in \mathbb{N} : b \geq a\}$. Let $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$. If $a > b$, then we set $\{a, \dots, b\} := \emptyset$. We denote by ε the empty sequence. Let s be a sequence. We denote by $|s|$ its length. Let $(s_1, \dots, s_{|s|}) := s$, and let $i, j \in \mathbb{N}$. If $i, j \in \{1, \dots, |s|\}$ and $i \leq j$, then we define $s[i..j] := (s_i, \dots, s_j)$. If $i > j$, then we set $s[i..j] := \varepsilon$. If $i \in \{1, \dots, |s|\}$, then we define $s[i] := s_i$. Thus, note that we use 1-based indexing.

0.2 Problem-Specific Notations

For the rest of this document, let Σ be a finite alphabet. For the rest of this subsection, let $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. We set $\Sigma_k := \Sigma^k$. We define $\Sigma_k^+ := \bigcup_{t \geq 1} \Sigma_k^t$ and $\Sigma_k^* := \Sigma_k^+ \cup \{\varepsilon\}$, where $\Sigma_k^t := \Sigma_k \times \dots \times \Sigma_k$ (t times) for all $t \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. Taking into account the case $k = 1$, we set $\Sigma^+ := \Sigma_1^+$ and $\Sigma^* := \Sigma_1^*$. Let $u \in \Sigma_k^*$. For all $s \in \Sigma_k^*$ and $i \in \{|u|, \dots, |s|\}$, we say that u ends at a position i of s iff $s[i-|u|+1..i] = u$. Throughout this document, when considering a sequence named x , we write n to denote its length. Similarly, we denote by m the length of a sequence named y . Let $x, y \in \Sigma_k^*$. If $k \leq n$, then we denote by $x^{(k)}$ the sequence $r \in \Sigma_k^{n-k+1}$ such that $r[i] = x[i..i+k-1]$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n-k+1\}$; if $k \leq m$, then we analogously define $y^{(k)}$. We describe u as a *factor* of x iff there exists an index of x at which it ends; similarly for y . Thus, note that ε is a factor of x . We describe u as a *common factor* of x and y iff u is a factor of x and a factor of y . We denote by $\text{CF}(x, y)$ the set of common factors of x and y . We describe u as a *longest common factor* of x and y iff $u \in \text{CF}(x, y)$ and $|u| \geq |s|$ for all $s \in \text{CF}(x, y)$. We denote by $\text{LCF}(x, y)$ the set of longest common factors of x and y . Let $(i, j) \in \{1, \dots, n\} \times \{1, \dots, m\}$. We define $\text{CF}_{i,j}(x, y)$ as the set of common factors of x and y ending, respectively, at positions i and j . That is, $\text{CF}_{i,j}(x, y) := \{s \in \text{CF}(x, y) : s = x[i-|s|+1..i] \wedge s = y[j-|s|+1..j]\}$. We define $\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)$ as the longest element of $\text{CF}_{i,j}(x, y)$. We define $\text{CF}_i(x, y)$ as the set of common factors of x and y ending at position i of x . We prefer the more neutral term *factor*, as opposed to *substring*, because we consider sequences over Σ_k .

0.3 Pseudocode Notations

Let arr be an array. We write for c in $\text{reversed}(\text{arr})$ to iterate over arr from right to left. We write $|\text{arr}|$ to denote the length of arr . For all $i, j \in \{1, \dots, |\text{arr}|\}$ with $i < j$, we write $\text{arr}[i..j]$ to denote an array arr' such that $|\text{arr}'| = j - i + 1$ and $\text{arr}'[p] = \text{arr}[p+i-1]$ for all $p \in \{1, \dots, |\text{arr}'|\}$.

0.4 Representation

Let arr be an array. We say that it represents the empty sequence iff arr is empty. We say that it represents a sequence $s \in \Sigma_k^+$, for some $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$, iff $|\text{arr}| = |s|$ and for all $i \in \{1, \dots, |s|\}$:

- if $s[i]$ is a symbol, then $\text{arr}[i]$ is a character equal to $s[i]$;
- otherwise, if $s[i]$ is a sequence, then $\text{arr}[i]$ is an array representing $s[i]$.

When talking about algorithms, we identify sequences with arrays. Suppose that $s \in \Sigma^+$ is the sequence represented by arr , and let h be a hash map (or a hash set). We assume that arr can be used as a key of h , and that hashing depends solely on s . We overload the symbol $=$ to also assert that the left-hand side represents the right-hand side. Let h be a hash map. We say that it represents a function f iff the set of keys of h equals $\text{dom}(f)$, and for each $k \in \text{dom}(f)$ we have that h stores the key-value pair $(k, f(k))$. We identify the elements of \mathbb{N} with the program variables representing them. For example, given $i \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$, we use the symbol i to denote both an element of $\mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$ and a pseudocode variable; the intended meaning will be clear from the context.

0.5 Complexity Assumptions

Any two symbols of Σ can be compared in constant time, and each requires $O(1)$ space to be stored. We consider only dynamic arrays. Let arr be an array. Each lookup on arr runs in $O(1)$ time, each append runs in (amortized) $O(1)$ time, and $|\text{arr}|$ is available in $O(1)$ time. Suppose that arr represents a sequence

$s \in \Sigma^+$. For all $i, j \in \{1, \dots, |s|\}$ with $i < j$, the construction of $\text{arr}[i..j]$ requires $O(j-i+1)$ time. Let h be either a hash map or a hash set. Each lookup on h , using s as the key, requires $O(|s|)$ expected time. If an operation attempts to insert arr as a key of h , then a copy of arr is stored instead. The copy can be computed in $O(|s|)$ time. The space required by h is linear in the cumulative size of its contents. Suppose that h is a hash map, and that (a, b) is a key-value pair it stores. If b is an array, then $h[a]$ returns a reference to it; otherwise, it returns a copy. Similarly for array lookups. Arrays and hash maps are passed (to functions) by reference, whereas integers are passed by value. The operation $\text{array}(\text{len}=n)$, with $n \in \mathbb{N}$, runs in $\Theta(n)$ time, while $\text{array}()$, $\text{HashMap}()$, and $\text{HashSet}()$ run in $O(1)$ time.

1 Introduction

1.1 Function $\lambda_k(x, y)$

This function allows us to express (part of) the time complexity of our algorithm. Given two sequences x and y , it returns the number of pairs $(i, j) \in \{1, \dots, n\} \times \{1, \dots, m\}$ such that $x[i] = y[j]$.

Definition 1.1.1. Let $n, m, k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. For all $(i, j) \in \{1, \dots, n\} \times \{1, \dots, m\}$, we define $c_{i,j} : \Sigma_k^n \times \Sigma_k^m \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ by $c_{i,j}(x, y) = 1$ iff $x[i] = y[j]$.

Definition 1.1.2. Let $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. We define $\lambda_k : \Sigma_k^* \times \Sigma_k^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ by:

$$\lambda_k(x, y) := \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m c_{i,j}(x, y)$$

if $x \neq \varepsilon \wedge y \neq \varepsilon$, and otherwise by $\lambda_k(x, y) := 0$.

Note: in the remainder of this document, whenever clear from context, we denote λ_k by λ .

1.2 Our Contribution

The longest common substring problem (LCSubstr) can be formalized as follows: given $x, y \in \Sigma^*$, return an element of $\text{LCF}(x, y)$. This is a classical problem, which can be solved in $O(n+m)$ time using suffix arrays [Babenko and Starikovskaya]. Nevertheless, we present an algorithm requiring $O(k^2(n+m) + \lambda_k(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}))$ expected amortized time¹ and $O(k(n+m))$ space, where $k \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$ is an additional parameter. Our approach is conceptually simple and straightforward to implement. We introduce it in subsection 1.3. As discussed in 2.10, if there exists $s \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$ such that $|s| \geq k$, then it requires $\Theta(k(n+m-k) + \lambda_k(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}))$ expected amortized time and $\Theta(k(n+m-k))$ space. In this case, bit-packing (if applicable) can further reduce the complexities, yielding $\Theta(n+m-k + \lambda_k(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}))$ expected amortized time and $\Theta(n+m-k)$ space. In section 2, we formally present our algorithm. In section 3, under an i.i.d. model², we provide evidence on the utility of k . A specific choice of this parameter (such that $k \in O(\log(nm))$) yields $\mathbb{E}[\lambda_k(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)})] \leq n+m$, as opposed to $\mathbb{E}[\lambda_1(x, y)] \in \Theta(nm)$ ³. This allows our algorithm to run in $O(\log^2(nm)(n+m))$ expected amortized time, with a probability not smaller than $1 - 1/\log^2(nm)$, while occupying $O(\log(nm)(n+m))$ space.

1.3 Deriving the Algorithm

We present our algorithm by starting from first principles. In order to better focus on the core logic, we suppress the parameter k (or, equivalently, we assume $k = 1$). Let $x, y \in \Sigma^+$ and $I := \{1, \dots, n\} \times \{1, \dots, m\}$. The following observation provides structural insight into the LCSubstr problem:

- (1) For each $s \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$, there exists a pair $(i, j) \in I$ such that $\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y) = s$.⁴

¹ Expected only due to hash map lookups/insertions; this also applies to the remaining time complexities of this subsection.

² We will assume that x and y are i.i.d. generated under some distribution on Σ .

³ We are abusing notation.

⁴ Let $s \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$. Since $s \in \text{CF}(x, y)$, there exists a pair $(i, j) \in I$ such that $s \in \text{CF}_{i,j}(x, y)$. Since $s \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$, the sequence s is the longest in $\text{CF}_{i,j}(x, y)$. Thus, $s = \text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)$

Thus, it suffices to consider the set of candidates $\{\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y) : (i, j) \in I\}$. Among these, a solution can be found by noting:

- (2) Let $(i, j) \in I$. If $|\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)| \geq |\text{lcf}_{i',j'}(x, y)|$ for all $(i', j') \in I$, then $\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y) \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$.⁵

This yields the following approach:

```

1 function lcf( $x, y$ )
2    $\text{ans} \leftarrow \varepsilon$ 
3   for  $(i, j) \in I$  do
4      $\text{cur} \leftarrow \text{compute } \text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)$ 
5     if  $|\text{cur}| > |\text{ans}|$  then
6        $\text{ans} \leftarrow \text{cur}$ 
7   return  $\text{ans}$ 

```

For each $(i, j) \in I$, the sequence $\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)$ can be computed by noting:

- (3) If $x[i] \neq y[j]$, then $\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y) = \varepsilon$. Suppose $x[i] = y[j]$. If $i = 1 \vee j = 1$, then $\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y) = x[i]$; otherwise, $\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y) = \text{lcf}_{i-1,j-1}(x, y) * x[i]$.⁶

This completes the above approach, which then requires $O(n \cdot m \cdot \min(n, m))$ time and $O(\min(n, m))$ space. The space complexity can be reduced to $O(1)$. It suffices to adapt (3) for computing $|\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)|$, and to observe:

- (4) Let $(p, q) \in I$ and $\ell := |\text{lcf}_{p,q}(x, y)|$. Suppose that $\ell \geq |\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)|$ for all $(i, j) \in I$. By (2), we have $\text{lcf}_{p,q}(x, y) \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$. The sequence $\text{lcf}_{p,q}(x, y)$ ends at position p of x and has length ℓ , thus $x[p-\ell+1..p] \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$.

We then obtain:

```

1 function lcf( $x, y$ )
2    $p \leftarrow -1$ 
3    $\ell \leftarrow 0$ 
4   for  $(i, j) \in I$  do
5      $\ell' \leftarrow \text{compute } |\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)|$ 
6     if  $\ell' > \ell$  then
7        $p \leftarrow i$ 
8        $\ell \leftarrow \ell'$ 
9   if  $p \geq 1$  then
10    return  $x[p-\ell+1..p]$ 
11  return  $\varepsilon$ 

```

Without loss of generality, suppose $n \geq m$. At the expense of $\Theta(m)$ space, the time complexity can be reduced to $\Theta(nm)$. Observe:

- (5) Let $(i, j) \in I$ with $i > 1 \wedge j > 1$. Our approach involves computing both $|\text{lcf}_{i-1,j-1}(x, y)|$ and $|\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)|$. However, if $x[i] = y[j]$, then the latter depends on the former (recall (3)). Thus, if we compute and store $|\text{lcf}_{i-1,j-1}(x, y)|$ before $|\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)|$, then the latter can be obtained in constant time, avoiding redundant calculations.

In short, (3) uncovers dynamic programming as a natural framework for improving the time complexity. In order to employ (5), we introduce an auxiliary array row of length m . Then, we iterate over I as follows: for each $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, traverse the indices $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ in reverse order. In fact, suppose that the algorithm has just begun the i -th iteration of its outer loop, with $i > 1$. Thus, suppose that for all $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ we have $\text{row}[j] = |\text{lcf}_{i-1,j}(x, y)|$. When the algorithm considers an element $j \in \{2, \dots, m\}$, it has $|\text{lcf}_{i-1,j-1}(x, y)|$ stored in $\text{row}[j-1]$. Consequently, it can compute and assign $|\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)|$ to $\text{row}[j]$ in $O(1)$ time. This yields the following algorithm:

⁵ Let $(i, j) \in I$. For all $(i', j') \in I$, if $|\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)| \geq |\text{lcf}_{i',j'}(x, y)|$, then $|\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)| \geq \max\{|s| : s \in \text{CF}_{i',j'}(x, y)\}$. Given that $\text{CF}(x, y)$ equals $\cup_{(i',j') \in I} \text{CF}_{i',j'}(x, y)$, we conclude that $\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y) \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$.

⁶ The asterisk denotes the concatenation operator

```

1 function lcf( $x, y$ )
2    $p \leftarrow -1$ 
3    $\ell \leftarrow 0$ 
4    $\text{row} \leftarrow \text{array}(\text{len} = |y|)$ 
5   for  $i=1$  to  $|x|$  do
6     for  $j=|y|$  to 1 do
7        $\ell' \leftarrow 0$ 
8       if  $x[i] = y[j]$  then
9         if  $i > 1 \wedge j > 1$  then
10           $\ell' \leftarrow \text{row}[j-1] + 1$ 
11        else
12           $\ell' \leftarrow 1$ 
13         $\text{row}[j] \leftarrow \ell'$ 
14        if  $\ell' > \ell$  then
15           $p \leftarrow i$ 
16           $\ell \leftarrow \ell'$ 
17    if  $p \geq 1$  then
18      return  $x[p-\ell+1..p]$ 
19    return  $\varepsilon$ 

```

Its time complexity can be refined to $\Theta(n + m + \lambda_1(x, y))$, albeit in expected and amortized terms, while still requiring $\Theta(m)$ space. The following observation exposes a key inefficiency of the above algorithm:

- (6) Let $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. At the start of the i -th iteration of the outer-loop, the variable ℓ contains a value not smaller than 0. Thus, for each $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ such that $|\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)| = 0$, the control at line 14 is guaranteed to fail.

That is, each pair $(i, j) \in I$ such that $x[i] \neq y[j]$ is irrelevant to improving the current best solution. However, due to the decomposition outlined in (3), it might be useful to know whether (i, j) is such that $|\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)| = 0$. In order to (implicitly) store this information, we modify each element of row to contain two fields: len and upd . During the initialization phase, we set to -1 the upd field of each element. Then, for each $(i, j) \in I$, we manipulate $\text{row}[j]$ as follows. If $x[i] \neq y[j]$, then we do not alter $\text{row}[j]$. Otherwise, we assign $|\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)|$ to $\text{row}[j].\text{len}$, and i to $\text{row}[j].\text{upd}$. In this second case, we can still compute $|\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)|$ in $O(1)$ time. In fact, suppose that $i > 1 \wedge j > 1$ (otherwise, it is trivial), and recall the specified iteration order. It suffices to check the value contained in $\text{row}[j-1].\text{upd}$. If it isn't $i-1$, then $x[i-1] = y[j-1]$ cannot be true. Thus, we establish that $|\text{lcf}_{i-1,j-1}(x, y)| = 0$. Suppose, instead, that it is $i-1$. By contradiction, suppose that $x[i-1] \neq y[j-1]$ holds. When processing the pair $(i-1, j-1)$, the algorithm cannot have modified $\text{row}[j-1]$. If no prior outer-loop iteration had modified $\text{row}[j-1].\text{upd}$, then now it would contain -1 (due to the initialization phase). This cannot have happened, since $i-1$ is at least 0. Suppose that there existed an outer-loop iteration during which $\text{row}[j-1].\text{upd}$ had been modified. Let i' identify the latest of those iterations. Currently, $\text{row}[j-1].\text{upd}$ would contain i' . However, i' necessarily belongs to $\{1, \dots, i-2\}$. Thus, $\text{row}[j-1].\text{upd} = i-1$ would be contradicted. Consequently, $x[i-1] \neq y[j-1]$ must be false. This implies that $\text{row}[j-1].\text{len}$ contains $|\text{lcf}_{i-1,j-1}(x, y)|$. By augmenting row , we have eliminated the need to consider any pair $(i, j) \in I$ such that $x[i] \neq y[j]$. In order to complete our algorithm, we need a means to iterate only over the remaining pairs of I . For this reason, during the initialization phase, we construct a hash map mapping each symbol σ of y to the strictly increasing ordering of $\{j \in \{1, \dots, m\} : y[j] = \sigma\}$. This can be done in $\Theta(m)$ expected amortized time and $\Theta(m)$ space.⁷ We defer the pseudocode to the next section, where we will account for the additional parameter k . We anticipate that k introduces a tradeoff: at the expense of replacing, in both complexities, the factor $n + m$ with $k(n + m - k)$ ⁸, we can substitute $\lambda_1(x, y)$ with $\lambda_k(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)})$.

⁷ The hash map might be replaceable with an array.

⁸ Or $n + m - k$, if bit-packing is used.

2 The Algorithm

2.1 Preliminaries

2.1.1 Type Cell

Definition 2.1.1. We define the type `Cell` to admit exactly two fields: `upd` and `len`. We write $\text{row} \in \text{Cell}^m$, for some $m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$, to assert that `row` is an array of m elements, each of type `Cell`. We write $\text{row}[j].\text{upd}$, for some $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, to denote the `upd` field of $\text{row}[j]$; analogously for `len`. In pseudocode, we write $\text{Cell}(\text{upd} = -1)$ to create an element of type `Cell` whose `upd` field contains -1 (the initial value of `len` is irrelevant). We assume that this operation runs in $O(1)$ time.

2.1.2 Function ends_y

Definition 2.1.2. Let $s \in \Sigma_k^+$, for some $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. For the purpose of the following definition, let $A_s := \{s[i] : i \in \{1, \dots, |s|\}\}$ and, for all $a \in A_s$, let $B_s(a) := \{i \in \{1, \dots, |s|\} : s[i] = a\}$. We define ends_s as the function, with domain A_s , that maps each $a \in A_s$ to the strictly increasing ordering of $B_s(a)$.

2.1.3 Property `rowConsistency`

Definition 2.1.3. Let $x \in \Sigma_k^*$ and $y \in \Sigma_k^+$, for some $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. Let $\text{row} \in \text{Cell}^m$. For all $i \in \{0, \dots, n\}$ and $j_1, j_2 \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, we introduce $\text{rowConsistency}_i(j_1, j_2)$ as follows. If $i = 0$, then we set it as:

$$\forall j \in \{j_1, \dots, j_2\} \quad \text{row}[j].\text{upd} = -1$$

Otherwise, we define it as:

$$\forall j \in \{j_1, \dots, j_2\} \quad \begin{cases} \text{row}[j].\text{upd} = i \wedge \text{row}[j].\text{len} = |\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)| & \text{if } x[i] = y[j] \\ \text{row}[j].\text{upd} < i & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

2.2 Function `buildMap`

Setup 2.2.1. Let $y \in \Sigma_k^+$, for some $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. Suppose that y is the input passed to `buildMap`, which is defined as follows:

```

1 function buildMap(y)
2   h ← hashMap()
3   for j=1 to |y| do
4     a ← y[j]
5     if a not in h then
6       h[a] ← array()
7       h[a].append(j)
8   return h

```

Statement 2.2.2. The algorithm returns a hash map representing ends_y , and does not alter y .

Statement 2.2.3. The algorithm requires $\Theta(km)$ expected amortized time and $\Theta(km)$ space.

2.3 Function `initRow`

Setup 2.3.1. Let $m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. Suppose that m is the input passed to `initRow`, which is defined as follows:

```

1 function initRow(m)
2   row ← array(len = m)
3   for j=1 to m do
4     row[j] ← Cell(upd = -1)
5   return row

```

Statement 2.3.2. The algorithm returns an array $\text{row} \in \text{Cell}^m$, such that $\text{row}[j].\text{upd} = -1$ for all $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$.

Statement 2.3.3. The algorithm requires $\Theta(m)$ time and space.

2.4 Procedure updRow

Setup 2.4.1. Let $x, y \in \Sigma_k^+$, for some $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. Let $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Let `lstEnds` be an array such that:

- if $x[i] \in \text{dom}(\text{ends}_y)$, then it represents $\text{ends}_y(x[i])$;
- otherwise, it is empty.

Let r_i denote the length of `lstEnds`. Finally, let $\text{row} \in \text{Cell}^m$ be such that $\text{rowConsistency}_{i-1}(1, m)$ holds. Suppose that i , `lstEnds` and `row` are the inputs passed to `updRow`, which is defined as follows:

```

1 procedure updRow(i, lstEnds, row)
2   for p in reversed(lstEnds) do
3     row[p].upd ← i
4     if p - 1 ≥ 1 ∧ row[p - 1].upd = i - 1 then
5       row[p].len ← row[p - 1].len + 1
6     else
7       row[p].len ← 1

```

Statement 2.4.2. Upon termination of `updRow`, the condition $\text{rowConsistency}_i(1, m)$ holds. Moreover, $\text{row} \in \text{Cell}^m$ is preserved and `lstEnds` is not altered.

Proof. The proof is deferred to [A.1](#).

Statement 2.4.3. The algorithm requires $\Theta(r_i)$ time and $O(1)$ space.

2.5 Function scanRow

Setup 2.5.1. Let $x, y \in \Sigma_k^+$, for some $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. Let $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Let `lstEnds` be an array such that:

- if $x[i] \in \text{dom}(\text{ends}_y)$, then it represents $\text{ends}_y(x[i])$;
- otherwise, it is empty.

Let r_i denote the length of `lstEnds`. Finally, let $\text{row} \in \text{Cell}^m$ be such that $\text{rowConsistency}_i(1, m)$ holds. Suppose that `lstEnds` and `row` are the inputs passed to `scanRow`, which is defined as follows:

```

1 function scanRow(lstEnds, row)
2   rowLen ← 0
3   for p in lstEnds do
4     if row[p].len > rowLen then
5       rowLen ← row[p].len
6   return rowLen

```

Statement 2.5.2. Without altering its input arrays, the algorithm returns $\max\{|s| : s \in \text{CF}_i(x, y)\}$.

Proof. The proof is deferred to [A.2](#).

Statement 2.5.3. The algorithm requires $\Theta(r_i)$ time and $O(1)$ space.

2.6 Function identify

Setup 2.6.1. Let $x, y \in \Sigma_k^+$, for some $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. Suppose that these are the inputs passed to `identify`, which is defined as follows:

```

1 function identify( $x, y$ )
2   ansEnd  $\leftarrow$  0
3   ansLen  $\leftarrow$  0
4   row  $\leftarrow$  initRow( $|y|$ )
5   mapEnds  $\leftarrow$  buildMap( $y$ )
6   for  $i=1$  to  $|x|$  do
7     lstEnds  $\leftarrow$  array()
8     if  $x[i]$  in mapEnds then
9       lstEnds  $\leftarrow$  mapEnds[ $x[i]$ ]
10    updRow( $i, lstEnds, row$ )
11    rowLen  $\leftarrow$  scanRow(lstEnds, row)
12    if rowLen  $>$  ansLen then
13      ansEnd  $\leftarrow$   $i$ 
14      ansLen  $\leftarrow$  rowLen
15  return [ansEnd, ansLen]
```

Statement 2.6.2. The algorithm returns a pair (i, ℓ) that satisfies the following. If $\text{LCF}(x, y) \neq \{\varepsilon\}$, then $x[i-\ell+1..i] \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$; otherwise, $(i, \ell) = (0, 0)$. Moreover, it does not alter x and y .

Proof. The proof is deferred to [A.3](#).

Statement 2.6.3. The algorithm requires $\Theta(k(n+m) + \lambda(x, y))$ expected amortized time and $\Theta(km)$ space.

Proof. The initialization phase requires $\Theta(km)$ expected amortized time and space. Moreover, each iteration requires $\Omega(k)$ expected time (due to the lookup at line 8) and $O(1)$ space (since at line 9 a reference is returned). Consequently, the algorithm requires $\Omega(k(n+m))$ expected amortized time and $\Theta(km)$ space. Let $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, and consider the i -th iteration. Let r_i denote the length of `lstEnds`, immediately before the execution of line 10. Ignoring the lookup at line 8, the iteration requires $O(r_i)$ expected time. It follows by the definitions of `endsy` and $c_{i,j}$ (see [1.1.1](#)) that $r_i = c_{i,1}(x, y) + \dots + c_{i,m}(x, y)$. Consequently, still ignoring the lookup at line 8, the execution of the loop requires $\Theta(\lambda(x, y))$ expected time. Therefore, the algorithm requires $\Theta(k(n+m) + \lambda(x, y))$ expected amortized time. \square

2.7 Function buildSequence

Setup 2.7.1. Let $s \in \Sigma^+$ and $k \in \{1, \dots, |s|\}$. Suppose that these are the inputs passed to `buildSequence`, which is defined as follows:

```

1 function buildSequence( $s, k$ )
2   arr  $\leftarrow$  array(len =  $|s| - k + 1$ )
3   for  $i=1$  to  $|s| - k + 1$  do
4     arr[ $i$ ]  $\leftarrow$   $s[i..i+k-1]$ 
5   return arr
```

Statement 2.7.2. Without altering s , the algorithm returns $s^{(k)}$.

Statement 2.7.3. The algorithm requires $\Theta(k|s| - k^2)$ time and space.

2.8 Function linearSearch

Remark 2.8.1. The following algorithm is an intentionally simplistic fallback. Mostly for this reason, the proof of [2.8.3](#) is informal (the remaining reason is that it follows by inspection). Similarly, in [2.8.4](#) we only present a loose bound. We chose this naive approach for brevity, as it is not the main contribution. Binary search could be used to achieve a better time complexity.

Setup 2.8.2. Let $x, y \in \Sigma^+$ and $t \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$. Suppose that these are the inputs passed to `linearSearch`, which is defined as follows:

```

1 function linearSearch( $x, y, t$ )
2   for  $\ell = t$  to 1 do
3      $h \leftarrow \text{hashSet}()$ 
4     for  $b$  in buildSequence( $x, \ell$ ) do
5        $h.add(b)$ 
6     for  $b$  in buildSequence( $y, \ell$ ) do
7       if  $b$  in  $h$  then
8         return  $b$ 
9   return array()
```

Statement 2.8.3. For the purpose of this statement, let $A(x, y) := \{s \in \text{CF}(x, y) : |s| \leq t\}$. Without altering x and y , the algorithm returns an element $s \in A(x, y)$ such that $|s| \geq |s'|$ for all $s' \in A(x, y)$.

Proof. During each iteration, thus considering some $\ell \in \{1, \dots, t\}$, the algorithm checks whether there exists a sequence of $A(x, y)$ having length ℓ . To this end, note that it considers every length- ℓ factor of x through `buildSequence(x, ℓ)`; similarly for y . If the check succeeds, then it returns one such sequence. Due to the iteration order, if it returns a sequence of length ℓ , then $A(x, y)$ contains no longer element (if it did, it would have been found during an earlier iteration). Similarly, if the check never succeeds, then $A(x, y)$ cannot contain a sequence longer than ε . □

Statement 2.8.4. The algorithm requires $O(t^2(n + m))$ expected time and $O(t(n + m))$ space.

Proof. For each $\ell \in \{1, \dots, t\}$, the corresponding iteration (if it is executed) requires $O(\ell(n + m))$ expected time and space. At the end of each iteration, all its auxiliary space is reclaimed; thus, the algorithm requires $O(t(n + m))$ space. In the worst case, t iterations are performed; since $(1 + \dots + t) \in O(t^2)$, the algorithm requires $O(t^2(n + m))$ expected time. □

2.9 Function `klcf`

Setup 2.9.1. Let $x, y \in \Sigma^*$. If $x = \varepsilon$ or $y = \varepsilon$, then let $k := 0$; otherwise, let $k \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$. Suppose that these are the inputs passed to `klcf`, which is defined as follows:

```

1 function klcf( $x, y, k$ )
2   if  $|x| = 0 \vee |y| = 0$  then
3     return array()
4    $x' \leftarrow \text{buildSequence}(x, k)$ 
5    $y' \leftarrow \text{buildSequence}(y, k)$ 
6    $i', \ell' \leftarrow \text{identify}(x', y')$ 
7   if  $i' \neq 0 \wedge \ell' \neq 0$  then
8      $i \leftarrow i' + k - 1$ 
9      $\ell \leftarrow \ell' + k - 1$ 
10  return  $x[i - \ell + 1 \dots i]$ 
11  return linearSearch( $x, y, k - 1$ )
```

Statement 2.9.2. Without altering x and y , the algorithm returns an element of $\text{LCF}(x, y)$.

Proof. The proof is deferred to [A.4](#).

Statement 2.9.3. The algorithm requires $O(k^2(n + m) + \lambda(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}))$ expected amortized time and $O(k(n + m))$ space.

Proof. Suppose that the check at line 2 fails. If the check at line 7 succeeds, then the algorithm requires $\Theta(k(n + m - k) + \lambda(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}))$ expected amortized time and $\Theta(k(n + m - k))$ space. In fact, the execution of lines 4 and 5 requires $\Theta(k(n + m - k))$ time and space. Moreover, the execution of line 6 requires

$\Theta(k(n+m-k) + \lambda(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}))$ expected amortized time and $\Theta(k(m-k))$ space, because $|x^{(k)}| = n-k+1$ and $|y^{(k)}| = m-k+1$. Finally, the execution of line 10 requires $\Theta(n)$ time and space. If the check at line 7 fails, then line 11 is executed. It requires $O(k^2(n+m))$ expected time and $O(k(n+m))$ space. Therefore, in either case, the algorithm requires $O(k^2(n+m) + \lambda(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}))$ expected amortized time and $O(k(n+m))$ space. \square

2.10 Efficiency Considerations

Let $x, y \in \Sigma^+$ and $k \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$. The execution of $\text{klcf}(x, y, k)$ requires $O(k^2(n+m) + \lambda(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}))$ expected amortized time and $O(k(n+m))$ space (see 2.9.3). However, as follows from 2.10.1, if there exists $s \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$ such that $|s| \geq k$, then the check at line 7 succeeds.⁹ If it succeeds, then our algorithm requires $\Theta(k(n+m-k) + \lambda(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}))$ expected amortized time and $\Theta(k(n+m-k))$ space (see the proof of 2.9.3). At this point, bit-packing might represent an useful optimization. Consider a model with machine-words having at least size $\log_2 |\Sigma| \cdot k$. Instead of representing $x^{(k)}$ directly, we could construct an array arr , with $|\text{arr}| = n-k+1$, such that $\text{arr}[i]$ is a machine-word encoding $x^{(k)}[i]$, for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n-k+1\}$. It could be constructed in $\Theta(n)$ time¹⁰, and would require $\Theta(n)$ space. Similarly for $y^{(k)}$. Without the need to modify anything except buildSequence , this would make our algorithm require $\Theta(n+m-k + \lambda(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}))$ expected amortized time and $\Theta(n+m-k)$ space. We conclude by noting two things. First, our implementation emphasizes clarity over speed. Second, if the check at like 7 fails, then linearSearch is executed; however, as mentioned in 2.8.1, such algorithm is a simplistic fallback.

Statement 2.10.1. Let $x, y \in \Sigma^+$ and $k \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$. Let (i', ℓ') be the pair returned by $\text{identify}(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)})$. If there exists $s \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$ such that $|s| \geq k$, then $i' \neq 0$ and $\ell' \neq 0$. The converse also holds.

Proof. Suppose that there exists $s \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$ such that $|s| \geq k$. By A.4.3, we have $\text{LCF}(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)}) \neq \{\varepsilon\}$. Thus, it follows by 2.6.2 that $x^{(k)}[i'-\ell'+1..i'] \in \text{LCF}(x^{(k)}, y^{(k)})$ holds. Consequently, we establish through A.4.4 that $i' \in \{1, \dots, n-k+1\}$ and $\ell' \in \{1, \dots, i'\}$, so $i' \neq 0$ and $\ell' \neq 0$. As for the converse, suppose that $i' \neq 0$ and $\ell' \neq 0$. By A.4.5, we have $i' \in \{1, \dots, n-k+1\}$ and $\ell' \in \{1, \dots, i'\}$. Let $i := i'+k-1$ and $\ell := \ell'+k-1$. By A.4.5 we also have $x[i-\ell+1..i] \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$. Since $i \in \{k, \dots, n\}$ and $\ell \in \{k, \dots, i\}$, we conclude that there exists $s \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$ such that $|s| \geq k$. \square

3 i.i.d. Model

3.1 Model and Notations

We set $\{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_{|\Sigma|}\} := \Sigma$. We define $\mathcal{D}^\Sigma := \{d : \Sigma \rightarrow [0, 1] \mid d(\sigma_1) + \dots + d(\sigma_{|\Sigma|}) = 1\}$. For all $d \in \mathcal{D}^\Sigma$, we set $\phi_d := d(\sigma_1)^2 + \dots + d(\sigma_{|\Sigma|})^2$. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. We overload the notation $S \in \Sigma^n$ to denote a sequence of length n , where $S[i]$ is drawn i.i.d. according to d , for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. However, we assume that this holds only for capital letters; that is, $X \in \Sigma^n$ identifies X as a sequence of random variables, while $x \in \Sigma^n$ identifies x as a sequence of symbols. For all $t \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, we define $S^{(t)} := (S[1..t], S[2..t+1], \dots, S[n-t+1..n])$. Finally, we set $\mathbb{R}_{>0} := \{x \in \mathbb{R} : x > 0\}$, $\mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}} := \mathbb{N}_{\geq 89}$ and $\mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma := \{d \in \mathcal{D}^\Sigma : \phi_d \leq 0.95\}$.

3.2 Random Variables T^t and $C_{i,j}^t$

Definition 3.2.1. Let $d \in \mathcal{D}^\Sigma$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. Moreover, let $t \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$. Finally, let $X \in \Sigma^n$ and $Y \in \Sigma^m$. For all $(i, j) \in \{1, \dots, n-t+1\} \times \{1, \dots, m-t+1\}$, we set $C_{i,j}^t := c_{i,j}(X^{(t)}, Y^{(t)})$ (see 1.1.1). Then, we define $T^t := \lambda_t(X^{(t)}, Y^{(t)})$ (see 1.1.2).

⁹ Note that the check is passed only in this case (see 2.10.1).

¹⁰ First, store $x[1..k]$ into a machine word w ; this requires $\Theta(k)$ time. Then, assign a copy of w to $\text{arr}[1]$; this requires $O(1)$ time. Next, update w as follows: 1) set to zero its first $\log_2 |\Sigma|$ most significant bits; 2) shift its content by $\log_2 |\Sigma|$ bits to the left; 3) store $x[k+1]$ in its first (starting from left) $\log_2 |\Sigma|$ bits. This makes w represent $x[2..k+1]$, and requires $O(1)$ time. Assign a copy of w to $\text{arr}[2]$, and continue for the remaining terms. The (entire) construction of arr runs in $\Theta(k+n-k)$ time.

3.3 Expectation of T^t

Statement 3.3.1. Let $d \in \mathcal{D}^\Sigma$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. Moreover, let $t \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$. Finally, let $X \in \Sigma^n$ and $Y \in \Sigma^m$. We have $\mathbb{E}[T^t] = (n - t + 1)(m - t + 1)\phi_d^t$.

Proof. For all $i \in \{1, \dots, n - t + 1\}$, let R_i^t denote $C_{i,1}^t + \dots + C_{i,m-t+1}^t$. By linearity of expectation:

$$\mathbb{E}[T^t] = \mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{i=1}^{n-t+1} R_i^t\right] = \sum_{i=1}^{n-t+1} \mathbb{E}[R_i^t] = \sum_{i=1}^{n-t+1} \mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{j=1}^{m-t+1} C_{i,j}^t\right] = \sum_{i=1}^{n-t+1} \sum_{j=1}^{m-t+1} \mathbb{E}[C_{i,j}^t]$$

For all $(i, j) \in \{1, \dots, n - t + 1\} \times \{1, \dots, m - t + 1\}$ we have $\mathbb{E}[C_{i,j}^t] = \phi_d^t$. This follows by the definition of $C_{i,j}^t$ (note that it is a Bernoulli variable) and by **B.3.2**. Therefore, $\mathbb{E}[T^t] = (n - t + 1)(m - t + 1)\phi_d^t$. \square

3.4 Function v

Definition 3.4.1. We define $v : (0, 1) \times \mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}} \times \mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ as:

$$v(r, n, m) := \frac{\ln(1/n + 1/m)}{\ln(r)}$$

We defer to **B.1** the proof that v is well-defined.

3.5 The Impact of k

Definition 3.5.1. For all $d \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}}$, with $n \geq m$, we define $k := \lceil v(\phi_d, n, m) \rceil$.

Statement 3.5.2. Let $d \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}}$, with $n \geq m$. The value k is well-defined and belongs to $\{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$.

Proof. The expression $\lceil v(\phi_d, n, m) \rceil$ is well-defined, because $\phi_d \in (0, 1)$ (see **B.2.2**). The value k is at least 1, because the codomain of v is $\mathbb{R}_{>0}$. The value k is at most m , as numerically verified in **B.2.7**. Therefore, $k \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$. \square

Statement 3.5.3. Let $d \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}}$, with $n \geq m$. Moreover, let $X \in \Sigma^n$ and $Y \in \Sigma^m$. We have $\mathbb{E}[T^1] \in \Theta(nm)$.

Proof. It follows by **3.3.1** that $\mathbb{E}[T^1] = nm\phi_d$. Since $\phi_d \in (0, 1)$ (see **B.2.2**), we have $\mathbb{E}[T^1] \in \Theta(nm)$. \square

Statement 3.5.4. Let $d \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}}$, with $n \geq m$. Moreover, let $X \in \Sigma^n$ and $Y \in \Sigma^m$. We have $\mathbb{E}[T^k] \leq n + m$.

Proof. We have $\phi_d \in (0, 1)$ (see **B.2.2**). Thus, the function ϕ_d^x is strictly decreasing on $[0, +\infty)$. Since $0 < v(\phi_d, n, m) \leq k$, it follows that $\phi_d^k \leq \phi_d^{v(\phi_d, n, m)}$. The random variable T^k is well-defined, as $k \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$ (see **3.5.2**). We have $\mathbb{E}[T^k] = (n - k + 1)(m - k + 1)\phi_d^k$ (see **3.3.1**), thus $\mathbb{E}[T^k] \leq (n - k + 1)(m - k + 1)\phi_d^{v(\phi_d, n, m)}$. Due to the logarithm base change formula:

$$\phi_d^{v(\phi_d, n, m)} = \phi_d^{\log_{\phi_d}(\frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{m})} = \frac{n + m}{nm}$$

So:

$$(n - k + 1)(m - k + 1)\phi_d^{v(\phi_d, n, m)} = (n - k + 1)(m - k + 1)\frac{n + m}{nm} \leq n + m$$

Therefore, $\mathbb{E}[T^k] \leq n + m$. \square

Statement 3.5.5. Let $d \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}}$, with $n \geq m$. Moreover, let $X \in \Sigma^n$ and $Y \in \Sigma^m$. Suppose that klcf is run on x, y and k , where x is a realization of X and y a realization of Y . Its execution requires $O(\log(nm)(n + m))$ space. Furthermore, with a probability of at least $1 - 1/\log^2(nm)$, it requires $O(\log^2(nm)(n + m))$ expected amortized time.

Proof. As proved in 2.9.3, for all $t \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$ the klcf algorithm requires $O(t^2(n + m) + \lambda(x^{(t)}, y^{(t)}))$ expected amortized time and $O(t(n + m))$ space. Recall that $k \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$ (see 3.5.2). As shown in (1), we have $k \in O(\log(nm))$. Consequently, the execution of $\text{klcf}(x, y, k)$ requires $O(\log(nm)(n + m))$ space. By definition, T^k equals $\lambda_k(X^{(k)}, Y^{(k)})$. As shown in (2), we have:

$$P(T^k < \log^2(nm)(n + m)) \geq 1 - \frac{1}{\log^2(nm)}$$

Therefore, the execution of $\text{klcf}(x, y, k)$ requires $O(\log^2(nm)(n + m))$ expected amortized time with a probability not smaller than $1 - 1/\log^2(nm)$.

(1) We have:

$$k = \left\lceil \frac{\ln((n + m)/(nm))}{\ln(\phi_d)} \right\rceil \leq \frac{\ln(n + m) - \ln(nm)}{\ln(\phi_d)} + 1$$

It follows by B.2.2 that $\ln(\phi_d) < 0$, while $\ln(n + m)$ is positive, thus:

$$\frac{\ln(n + m) - \ln(nm)}{\ln(\phi_d)} + 1 = \frac{\ln(n + m)}{\ln(\phi_d)} - \frac{\ln(nm)}{\ln(\phi_d)} + 1 \leq -\frac{\ln(nm)}{\ln(\phi_d)} + 1$$

Consequently, $k \in O(\log(nm))$.

(2) We have:

$$P(T^k < \log^2(nm)(n + m)) = 1 - P(T^k \geq \log^2(nm)(n + m))$$

By Markov's inequality and 3.5.4:

$$P(T^k \geq \log^2(nm)(n + m)) \leq \frac{\mathbb{E}[T^k]}{\log^2(nm)(n + m)} \leq \frac{n + m}{\log^2(nm)(n + m)} = \frac{1}{\log^2(nm)}$$

Consequently:

$$P(T^k < \log^2(nm)(n + m)) \geq 1 - \frac{1}{\log^2(nm)}$$

□

A Correctness Proofs

A.1 Correctness of updRow

Proof of 2.4.2. It follows by inspection that the execution preserves $\text{row} \in \text{Cell}^m$, and that it does not alter lstEnds or i . Consequently, we will omit these conditions from the following invariant. Recall that, at the start of the execution, the condition $\text{rowConsistency}_{i-1}(1, m)$ holds. Let P denote the set of values contained in lstEnds . If $P = \emptyset$, then the algorithm terminates immediately. It follows by (1) (with $a = 1$ and $b = m$) that, at this point, $\text{rowConsistency}_i(1, m)$ holds. Suppose that $P \neq \emptyset$. Let $(p_1, \dots, p_r) := \text{ends}_y(x[i])$. Then, for all $s \in \{1, \dots, r\}$ let:

$$\text{Inv}(p_s) \quad := \quad \text{rowConsistency}_{i-1}(1, p_s - 1) \wedge \text{rowConsistency}_i(p_s, m)$$

and let $\text{it}(s)$ denote the iteration during which the variable p contains the value p_s . As a base case, in (2) we prove that at the end of $\text{it}(r)$ the condition $\text{Inv}(p_r)$ holds. As an inductive step, under the assumption that $r > 1$, in (3) we prove: for all $s \in \{1, \dots, r-1\}$, if at the start of $\text{it}(s)$ the condition $\text{Inv}(p_{s+1})$ holds, then at the end of $\text{it}(s)$ the condition $\text{Inv}(p_s)$ holds. Regardless of whether $r = 1$ or $r > 1$, it follows by induction that, at the end of $\text{it}(1)$, we have that $\text{Inv}(p_1)$ is true. Recall that $p_1 = \min P$. If $p_1 > 1$, then it follows by (1) (with $a = 1$ and $b = p_1 - 1$) that, at this point, $\text{rowConsistency}_i(1, p_1 - 1)$ holds. Therefore, regardless of whether $p_1 = 1$ or $p_1 > 1$, at the end of the execution $\text{rowConsistency}_i(1, m)$ holds.

(1) Let $a, b \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ be such that $\{a, \dots, b\} \cap P = \emptyset$. If $\text{rowConsistency}_{i-1}(a, b)$ holds, then $\text{rowConsistency}_i(a, b)$ also holds. In fact, for all $q \in \{a, \dots, b\}$ the former ensures that $\text{row}[q].\text{upd} \leq i-1$, while the latter requires that $\text{row}[q].\text{upd} < i$, as $x[i]$ is necessarily different from $y[q]$.

(2) We show that at the end of $\text{it}(r)$ the condition $\text{Inv}(p_r)$ is satisfied. During this iteration, $\text{row}[p_r]$ is the only element of row that is altered. Consequently, at its end:

- if $p_r > 1$, then $\text{rowConsistency}_{i-1}(1, p_r - 1)$ is preserved;
- if $p_r < m$, then it follows by (1) (with $a = p_r + 1$ and $b = m$) that $\text{rowConsistency}_i(p_r + 1, m)$ is satisfied, since $p_r = \max P$.

In all cases, it remains to verify that $\text{rowConsistency}_i(p_r, p_r)$ also holds at that point. To this end, we note that this condition is the conjunction of $\text{row}[p_r].\text{upd} = i$ and $\text{row}[p_r].\text{len} = |\text{lcf}_{i, p_r}(x, y)|$, since $x[i] = y[p_r]$. The first conjunct is satisfied by the execution of line 3. For the second, we recall that $p_r \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ and $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$; then, we distinguish three cases:

- Suppose $p_r = 1$. We have $|\text{lcf}_{i, p_r}(x, y)| = 1$. The check at line 4 fails. Consequently, $\text{row}[p_r].\text{len}$ is correctly assigned the value 1.
- Suppose $p_r \in \{2, \dots, m\}$ and $i = 1$. We have $|\text{lcf}_{i, p_r}(x, y)| = 1$. The check at line 4 fails, as $\text{rowConsistency}_{i-1}(p_r - 1, p_r - 1)$ ensures that $\text{row}[p_r - 1].\text{upd}$ was initialized with -1 . Consequently, $\text{row}[p_r].\text{len}$ is correctly assigned the value 1.
- Suppose $p_r \in \{2, \dots, m\}$ and $i \in \{2, \dots, n\}$. Considering that $|\text{lcf}_{i, p_r}(x, y)| = |\text{lcf}_{i-1, p_r-1}(x, y)| + 1$, we distinguish two subcases. Suppose that $x[i-1] \neq y[p_r - 1]$. We have $|\text{lcf}_{i, p_r}(x, y)| = 1$. The check at line 4 fails, as $\text{rowConsistency}_{i-1}(p_r - 1, p_r - 1)$ ensures that $\text{row}[p_r - 1].\text{upd} < i-1$ holds. Consequently, $\text{row}[p_r].\text{len}$ is correctly assigned the value 1. Instead, suppose that $x[i-1] = y[p_r - 1]$. The condition $\text{rowConsistency}_{i-1}(p_r - 1, p_r - 1)$ ensures that both $\text{row}[p_r - 1].\text{upd} = i-1$ and $\text{row}[p_r - 1].\text{len} = |\text{lcf}_{i-1, p_r-1}(x, y)|$ hold. Therefore, the check at line 4 succeeds and $\text{row}[p_r - 1].\text{upd}$ is correctly assigned the value $|\text{lcf}_{i-1, p_r-1}(x, y)| + 1$.

(3) Suppose $r > 1$, and let $s \in \{1, \dots, r-1\}$. Moreover, suppose that at the start of $\text{it}(s)$ the condition $\text{Inv}(p_{s+1})$, that is $\text{rowConsistency}_{i-1}(1, p_{s+1} - 1) \wedge \text{rowConsistency}_i(p_{s+1}, m)$, holds. During $\text{it}(s)$, the only element of row that is modified is $\text{row}[p_s]$. Moreover, the value p_s is smaller than p_{s+1} . Consequently, at the end of $\text{it}(s)$ the conditions $\text{rowConsistency}_{i-1}(1, p_s - 1)$ and $\text{rowConsistency}_i(p_{s+1}, m)$ are satisfied. At that point, the condition $\text{rowConsistency}_i(p_s, p_s)$ also holds. This follows by an argument analogous to that presented for $\text{rowConsistency}_i(p_r, p_r)$ in (2). If $p_s = p_{s+1} - 1$, then we have shown that, at the end of $\text{it}(s)$, the condition $\text{Inv}(p_s)$ holds. Otherwise, if $p_s < p_{s+1} - 1$, then the following observation allows us to reach the same conclusion. By the inductive hypothesis, the condition $\text{rowConsistency}_{i-1}(p_s + 1, p_{s+1} - 1)$ holds.

Moreover, the sequence (p_1, \dots, p_r) is strictly increasing. Consequently, it follows by (1) (with $a = p_s + 1$ and $b = p_{s+1} - 1$) that, at the end of it(s), the condition $\text{rowConsistency}_i(p_s + 1, p_{s+1} - 1)$ holds. \square

A.2 Correctness of scanRow

Proof of 2.5.2. Let P denote the set of values contained in lstEnds . We distinguish two cases. Suppose that $P = \emptyset$. As it follows by the definition of ends_y , we have $x[i] \neq y[j]$ for all $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$. Thus, $\text{CF}_i(x, y) = \{\varepsilon\}$. In this case, the algorithm correctly returns 0. Suppose that $P \neq \emptyset$. The precondition ensures that $\text{rowConsistency}_i(1, m)$ holds. Thus, at the start of the execution we have $\text{row}[p].\text{len} = |\text{lcf}_{i,p}(x, y)|$ for all $p \in P$. Let ℓ denote the value returned by the algorithm, that is $\max\{|\text{lcf}_{i,p}(x, y)| : p \in P\}$. As it follows by the definition of ends_y , for all $q \in \{1, \dots, m\} \setminus P$ we have $x[i] \neq y[q]$ and thus $|\text{lcf}_{i,q}(x, y)| = 0$. Consequently, for all $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ it holds that $\ell \geq |\text{lcf}_{i,j}(x, y)|$, that is $\ell \geq \max\{|s| : s \in \text{CF}_{i,j}(x, y)\}$. For all $s \in \text{CF}_i(x, y)$ there exists $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ such that $s \in \text{CF}_{i,j}(x, y)$, so $\ell \geq \max\{|s| : s \in \text{CF}_i(x, y)\}$. The value ℓ is the length of $\text{lcf}_{i,p}(x, y)$ for some $p \in P$, so $\ell \leq \max\{|s| : s \in \text{CF}_i(x, y)\}$. Therefore, $\ell = \max\{|s| : s \in \text{CF}_i(x, y)\}$. \square

A.3 Correctness of identify

Definition A.3.1. Let $x \in \Sigma_k^*$ and $y \in \Sigma_k^+$, for some $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. We define $\text{ansLen}(x, y)$ as the length of any element in $\text{LCF}(x, y)$. Moreover, we define:

$$\text{ansEnd}(x, y) := \begin{cases} \min A(x, y) & \text{if } \text{ansLen}(x, y) > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where $A(x, y)$ denotes the auxiliary set $\{i \in \{1, \dots, n\} : \exists s \in \text{LCF}(x, y) \ s = x[i - |s| + 1 \dots i]\}$.

Proof of 2.6.2. By inspection of the pseudocode of `identify` and `buildMap`, it follows that the algorithm never modifies the inputs x and y . Moreover, it does not alter `mapEnds` (after its initialization). Finally, if it alters `row`, then the modification is caused by `updRow` (not by `scanRow`, see 2.5.2), which ensures that $\text{row} \in \text{Cell}^m$ is preserved (see 2.4.2). In addition to partially satisfying the postcondition of `identify`, these observations allow us to consider the following, simplified, invariant.¹¹ For all $i \in \{0, \dots, n\}$, regarding the for loop, we define:

$$\text{Inv}(i) := \text{ansEnd} = \text{ansEnd}(x[1 \dots i], y) \wedge \text{ansLen} = \text{ansLen}(x[1 \dots i], y) \wedge \text{rowConsistency}_i(1, m)$$

Moreover, we define the postcondition `Post` as the conjunction of $\text{ansEnd} = \text{ansEnd}(x, y)$ and $\text{ansLen} = \text{ansLen}(x, y)$. Immediately before the first iteration, the condition $\text{Inv}(0)$ is true. As shown in (1), for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ we have: if at the start of the i -th iteration $\text{Inv}(i-1)$ holds, then at its end $\text{Inv}(i)$ holds. By induction, immediately after the last iteration the condition $\text{Inv}(n)$ is true. Thus, at this point `Post` holds. If $\text{LCF}(x, y) \neq \{\varepsilon\}$, then $\text{ansEnd}(x, y)$ and $\text{ansLen}(x, y)$ identify an element of $\text{LCF}(x, y)$. Otherwise, they are both equal to zero. Therefore, the array returned at line 15 satisfies the conditions stated in 2.6.2.

(1) Consider the i -th iteration. After its initial assignment, the variable i is not modified. Immediately before line 10, if $x[i] \in \text{dom}(\text{ends}_y)$, then lstEnds represents $\text{ends}_y(x[i])$; otherwise, it is empty. This array is not altered thereafter. By the inductive hypothesis, at this point $\text{rowConsistency}_{i-1}(x, y)$ holds; thus, immediately after the execution of line 10, $\text{rowConsistency}_i(x, y)$ holds (see 2.4.2). This satisfies the precondition of `scanRow`, which returns $\max\{|s| : s \in \text{CF}_i(x, y)\}$ (see 2.5.2). Let ℓ_{new} denote this value. Moreover, let ℓ_{cur} denote $\max\{|s| : s \in \text{CF}(x[1 \dots i-1], y)\}$. We proceed by characterizing $\text{ansEnd}(x[1 \dots i], y)$ and $\text{ansLen}(x[1 \dots i], y)$. However, we first note that:

$$\text{CF}(x[1 \dots i], y) = \text{CF}(x[1 \dots i-1], y) \cup \text{CF}_i(x, y)$$

In fact, each $s \in \text{CF}(x[1 \dots i], y)$ either ends at position i of x (in which case $s \in \text{CF}_i(x, y)$), or it does not (in which case $s \in \text{CF}(x[1 \dots i-1], y)$). Thus, $\text{CF}(x[1 \dots i], y) \subseteq \text{CF}(x[1 \dots i-1], y) \cup \text{CF}_i(x, y)$. The converse holds trivially. We proceed by distinguishing two cases:

¹¹For brevity, we omit the conditions that x and `mapEnds` retain their initial values, as well as $\text{row} \in \text{Cell}^m$ remaining true, across iterations.

- Suppose $\ell_{\text{new}} > \ell_{\text{cur}}$. Let $s \in \text{CF}_i(x, y)$ be such that $|s| = \ell_{\text{new}}$. For all $s' \in \text{CF}(x[1..i-1], y)$ we have $|s| > |s'|$, since $\ell_{\text{cur}} \geq |s'|$. Due to the above set equality we have $s \in \text{CF}(x[1..i], y)$, and also that $|s| \geq |s'|$ for all $s' \in \text{CF}(x[1..i], y)$. Thus, $s \in \text{LCF}(x[1..i], y)$. Consequently, we establish $\text{ansLen}(x[1..i], y) = \ell_{\text{new}}$. Regarding $\text{ansEnd}(x[1..i], y)$, we make two observations. First, we note that $\text{ansLen}(x[1..i], y) > 0$. This is because $\ell_{\text{new}} > \ell_{\text{cur}}$ and $\ell_{\text{cur}} \geq 0$. Second, we note that $\text{LCF}(x[1..i], y) \subseteq \text{CF}_i(x, y)$. In fact, we have $\text{LCF}(x[1..i], y) \subseteq \text{CF}(x[1..i], y)$ and $\text{LCF}(x[1..i], y) \cap \text{CF}(x[1..i-1], y) = \emptyset$. The latter is because $\text{CF}(x[1..i-1], y)$ contains only sequences whose length is strictly less than ℓ_{new} . Thus, our second observation follows by the above set equality. Therefore, we establish $\text{ansLen}(x[1..i], y) = i$.
- Suppose $\ell_{\text{new}} \leq \ell_{\text{cur}}$. By definition, $\ell_{\text{cur}} = \text{ansLen}(x[1..i-1], y)$. Suppose that $\ell_{\text{cur}} = 0$. This implies $\ell_{\text{new}} = 0$. Thus, by the above set equality, we have $\varepsilon \in \text{LCF}(x[1..i], y)$. Consequently, $\text{ansLen}(x[1..i], y) = \text{ansLen}(x[1..i-1], y) = 0$, and so $\text{ansEnd}(x[1..i], y) = \text{ansEnd}(x[1..i-1], y) = 0$. Suppose that $\ell_{\text{cur}} > 0$. If it were $i = 1$, then this hypothesis would be contradicted (recall the definition of ℓ_{cur}). So, we have $i \geq 2$. For all $s \in \text{LCF}(x[1..i-1], y)$, let $\text{pos}(s) := \min\{p \in \{|s|, \dots, i-1\} : x[p-|s|+1..p] = s\}$. Let $u \in \text{LCF}(x[1..i-1], y)$ be such that $\text{pos}(u) \leq \text{pos}(s)$, for all $s \in \text{LCF}(x[1..i-1], y)$. The length of u is ℓ_{cur} . Since $\ell_{\text{new}} \leq \ell_{\text{cur}}$, it follows by the above set equality that $u \in \text{LCF}(x[1..i], y)$. Thus, we establish $\text{ansLen}(x[1..i], y) = \text{ansLen}(x[1..i-1], y)$. We conclude by proving that $\text{ansEnd}(x[1..i], y) = \text{ansEnd}(x[1..i-1], y)$. Recall that $\ell_{\text{cur}} > 0$, and note that $\text{ansEnd}(x[1..i-1], y) = \text{pos}(u)$. Let $s \in \text{LCF}(x[1..i], y)$. We distinguish two cases. If $s \in \text{LCF}(x[1..i-1], y)$, then clearly $\text{pos}(u) \leq \text{pos}(s)$. Otherwise, if $s \notin \text{LCF}(x[1..i-1], y)$, then $s \notin \text{CF}(x[1..i-1], y)$. To see why, it suffices to consider the contrapositive (and to recall that $|s| = \ell_{\text{cur}}$). Since $s \in \text{CF}(x[1..i], y)$, it follows by the above set equality that $s \in \text{CF}_i(x, y)$. Note that $\text{pos}(u) \leq i-1$. Regardless of which case holds, we found: for all $s \in \text{LCF}(x[1..i], y)$ we have $\text{pos}(u) \leq p$, where p denotes the smallest position of $x[1..i]$ at which s ends. Therefore, $\text{ansEnd}(x[1..i], y) = \text{pos}(u)$.

Immediately before line 12, the variable `rowLen` contains ℓ_{new} . Moreover, the variables `ansLen` and `ansEnd` contain the values ℓ_{cur} and $\text{ansEnd}(x[1..i], y)$, respectively. This follows by the inductive hypothesis, and by the equality $\ell_{\text{cur}} = \text{ansLen}(x[1..i-1], y)$. The algorithm completes the iteration by adhering to the above case logic. Therefore, at the end of the i -th iteration, the condition $\text{Inv}(i)$ holds. \square

A.4 Correctness of `klcf`

Statement A.4.1. Let $x, y \in \Sigma^+$, and let $k \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$. Moreover, let $i' \in \{1, \dots, n-k+1\}$, $\ell' \in \{1, \dots, i'\}$, $x' := x^{(k)}$ and $y' := y^{(k)}$. Finally, let $i := i' + k - 1$ and $\ell := \ell' + k - 1$. If $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i'] \in \text{CF}(x', y')$, then $x[i-\ell+1..i] \in \text{CF}(x, y)$.

Proof. The sequence $x[i-\ell+1..i]$ is well-defined, since $i \in \{k, \dots, n\}$ and $\ell \in \{k, \dots, i\}$. Suppose that $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i'] \in \text{CF}(x', y')$. By definition of common factor, there exists $j' \in \{1, \dots, m-k+1\}$ such that $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i'] = y'[j'-\ell'+1..j']$. Let $j := j' + k - 1$. The sequence $y[j-\ell+1..j]$ is well-defined (same argument as above). As proved in (1), we have $x[i-k+1..i] = y[j-k+1..j]$. As proved in (2), if $\ell > k$ then $x[i-\ell+1..i-k] = y[j-\ell+1..j-k]$. Regardless of whether $\ell = k$ or $\ell > k$ ($\ell' \geq 1$ implies $\ell \geq k$), we establish that $x[i-\ell+1..i] = y[j-\ell+1..j]$. Therefore, $x[i-\ell+1..i] \in \text{CF}(x, y)$.

(1) As we know, $x'[i']$ equals $y'[j']$. By definition of x' and y' , the elements $x'[i']$ and $y'[j']$ are equal to $x[i'..i'+k-1]$ and $y[j'..j'+k-1]$, respectively. In turn, as it follows by the definition of i' and j' , those elements are equal to $x[i-k+1..i]$ and $y[j-k+1..j]$, respectively. Thus, $x[i-k+1..i] = y[j-k+1..j]$.

(2) Suppose $\ell > k$, and let $t \in \{1, \dots, \ell-k\}$. We have $i'-\ell' = i-\ell$, $j'-\ell' = j-\ell$ and $t \in \{1, \dots, \ell'\}$. Thus, $x'[i'-\ell'+t] = y'[j'-\ell'+t]$. By definition of x' and y' , the elements $x'[i'-\ell'+t]$ and $y'[j'-\ell'+t]$ are equal to $x[i-\ell+t..i-\ell+t+k-1]$ and $y[j-\ell+t..j-\ell+t+k-1]$, respectively. Thus, $x[i-\ell+t] = y[j-\ell+t]$. Consequently, $x[i-\ell+1..i-k] = y[j-\ell+1..j-k]$. \square

Statement A.4.2. Let $x, y \in \Sigma^+$, and let $k \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$. Moreover, let $i \in \{k, \dots, n\}$, $\ell \in \{k, \dots, i\}$, $x' := x^{(k)}$ and $y' := y^{(k)}$. Finally, let $i' := i-k+1$ and $\ell' := \ell-k+1$. If $x[i-\ell+1..i] \in \text{CF}(x, y)$, then $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i'] \in \text{CF}(x', y')$.

Proof. Suppose that $x[i-\ell+1..i] \in \text{CF}(x, y)$. By definition of common factor, there exists $j \in \{k, \dots, m\}$ such that $x[i-\ell+1..i] = y[j-\ell+1..j]$. Let $t' \in \{1, \dots, \ell'\}$. For all $q \in \{t', \dots, t'+k-1\}$, we have $x[i-\ell+q] = y[j-\ell+q]$. In fact, $\{t', \dots, t'+k-1\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, \ell\}$ and thus $q \in \{1, \dots, \ell\}$. Then, $x[i-\ell+t'..i-\ell+t'+(k-1)]$ equals $y[j-\ell+t'..j-\ell+t'+(k-1)]$. The element $x'[i-\ell+t']$ is well-defined. In fact, we have $i-\ell+t' \geq 1$ because $\ell \leq i$ and $t' \geq 1$; moreover, $i-\ell+t' \leq i-\ell+(\ell-k+1) = i-k+1 \leq n-k+1$. Analogously, $y'[j-\ell+t']$ is well-defined. By definition of x' and y' , we have $x'[i-\ell+t'] = x[i-\ell+t'..i-\ell+t'+(k-1)]$ and $y'[j-\ell+t'] = y[j-\ell+t'..j-\ell+t'+(k-1)]$. Thus, $x'[i-\ell+t'] = y'[j-\ell+t']$. Let $j' := j-k+1$. We have $i'-\ell' = i-\ell$ and $j'-\ell' = j-\ell$, so $x'[i'-\ell'+t'] = y'[j'-\ell'+t']$. The value t' was arbitrarily chosen in $\{1, \dots, \ell'\}$, thus $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i'] = y'[j'-\ell'+1..j']$. Therefore, $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i'] \in \text{CF}(x', y')$. \square

Statement A.4.3. Let $x, y \in \Sigma^+$ and $k \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$. Moreover, let $x' := x^{(k)}$ and $y' := y^{(k)}$. If there exists $s \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$ such that $|s| \geq k$, then $\text{LCF}(x', y') \neq \{\varepsilon\}$.

Proof. Suppose that there exists $s \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$ such that $|s| \geq k$. Let $\ell := |s|$. By definition of factor, there exists $i \in \{k, \dots, n\}$ such that $x[i-\ell+1..i] = s$. Note that $\ell \in \{k, \dots, i\}$. Let $i' := i-k+1$ and $\ell' := \ell-k+1$. It follows by A.4.2 that $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i'] \in \text{CF}(x', y')$. We have $i' \in \{1, \dots, n-k+1\}$ and $\ell' \in \{1, \dots, i'\}$; thus, $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i'] \neq \varepsilon$. Therefore, $\text{LCF}(x', y') \neq \{\varepsilon\}$. \square

Statement A.4.4. Let $x, y \in \Sigma^+$ and $k \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$. Moreover, let $x' := x^{(k)}$ and $y' := y^{(k)}$. Suppose that (i', ℓ') is a pair such that $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i'] \in \text{LCF}(x', y')$ holds, and suppose that $\text{LCF}(x', y') \neq \{\varepsilon\}$. Then, $i' \in \{1, \dots, n-k+1\}$ and $\ell' \in \{1, \dots, i'\}$.

Proof. Since $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i'] \in \text{LCF}(x', y')$ holds, the sequence $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i']$ is well-defined. Since $\text{LCF}(x', y') \neq \{\varepsilon\}$ holds, $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i']$ is not empty. Thus, $i'-\ell'+1, i' \in \{1, \dots, n-k+1\}$ and $i'-\ell'+1 \leq i'$ (see 0.1). Since $i'-\ell'+1 \geq 1$ and $i'-\ell'+1 \leq i'$, that is $\ell' \leq i'$ and $\ell' \geq 1$, we conclude that $i' \in \{1, \dots, n-k+1\}$ and $\ell' \in \{1, \dots, i'\}$. \square

Statement A.4.5. Let $x, y \in \Sigma^+$ and $k \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$. Let $x' := x^{(k)}$ and $y' := y^{(k)}$. Let (i', j') be the pair returned by `identify`(x', y'), and suppose that $(i', \ell') \neq (0, 0)$. We have $i' \in \{1, \dots, n-k+1\}$ and $\ell' \in \{1, \dots, i'\}$. Let $i := i'+k-1$ and $\ell := \ell'+k-1$. We also have $x[i-\ell+1..i] \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$.

Proof. Since $(i', \ell') \neq (0, 0)$, it follows by 2.6.2 that $\text{LCF}(x', y') \neq \{\varepsilon\}$ holds. Then, again by 2.6.2, we have $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i'] \in \text{LCF}(x', y')$. Thus, A.4.4 ensures that $i' \in \{1, \dots, n-k+1\}$ and $\ell' \in \{1, \dots, i'\}$. Since $i-\ell+1 = i'-\ell'+1 \geq 1$ and $i = i'+k-1 \leq n$, the element $x[i-\ell+1..i]$ is well-defined. Note that $\ell \geq k$. By contradiction, suppose that $x[i-\ell+1..i] \notin \text{LCF}(x, y)$. We have $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i'] \in \text{CF}(x', y')$, so $x[i-\ell+1..i] \in \text{CF}(x, y)$ by A.4.1. Due to this and the hypothesis that $x[i-\ell+1..i] \notin \text{LCF}(x, y)$, there exists $s \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$ such that $|s| > \ell$. Let $\ell_2 := |s|$. By definition of factor, we have $x[i_2-\ell_2+1..i_2] = s$ for some $i_2 \in \{k, \dots, n\}$. Note that $\ell_2 \in \{k, \dots, i_2\}$. Let $i'_2 := i_2-k+1$ and $\ell'_2 := \ell_2-k+1$. It follows by A.4.2 that $x'[i'_2-\ell'_2+1..i'_2] \in \text{CF}(x', y')$. This leads to a contradiction. In fact, $\ell_2 > \ell$ implies $\ell'_2 > \ell'$, thus $x'[i'-\ell'+1..i'] \in \text{LCF}(x', y')$ is false. Therefore, $x[i-\ell+1..i] \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$ must be true. \square

Proof of 2.9.2. First, note that the algorithm does not alter (not even through function calls) the arrays representing x and y . If $x = \varepsilon$ or $y = \varepsilon$, then $\text{LCF}(x, y) = \{\varepsilon\}$. In this case, the algorithm correctly returns an empty array. Suppose that $x, y \in \Sigma^+$. Let $x' := x^{(k)}$ and $y' := y^{(k)}$. Moreover, let i' and ℓ' denote, respectively, the values assigned to the variables i' and ℓ' at line 6. Considering 2.6.2, we distinguish two cases:

- Suppose $(i', \ell') \neq (0, 0)$. We know by A.4.5 that $i' \neq 0$ and $\ell' \neq 0$, thus the check at line 7 succeeds. Let $i := i'+k-1$ and $\ell := \ell'+k-1$. Again by A.4.5, we have that $x[i-\ell+1..i] \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$. Therefore, the algorithm returns an element of $\text{LCF}(x, y)$.
- Suppose $(i', \ell') = (0, 0)$. Let $A(x, y) := \{s \in \text{CF}(x, y) : |s| \leq k-1\}$. Clearly, $A(x, y) \subseteq \text{CF}(x, y)$. As shown in (1), the length of each element of $\text{LCF}(x, y)$ is smaller than k ; thus, $\text{CF}(x, y) \subseteq A(x, y)$. The algorithm executes line 11. The value it returns, let it be s , is such that $|s| \geq |s'|$ for all $s' \in A(x, y)$ (see 2.8.3). Since $A(x, y) = \text{CF}(x, y)$, the algorithm returns an element of $\text{LCF}(x, y)$.

(1) We have $(i', \ell') = (0, 0)$. Suppose that $\text{LCF}(x', y') \neq \{\varepsilon\}$. Then, since $x[i' - \ell' + 1 \dots i'] = \varepsilon$, we have $x[i' - \ell' + 1 \dots i'] \notin \text{LCF}(x', y')$. However, it follows by 2.6.2 that $x[i' - \ell' + 1 \dots i'] \in \text{LCF}(x', y')$. Consequently, $\text{LCF}(x', y') \neq \{\varepsilon\}$ cannot be true. We conclude through the following. If there existed $s \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$ such that $|s| \geq k$, then it would follow by A.4.3 that $\text{LCF}(x', y') \neq \{\varepsilon\}$. This would contradict what we just established. Therefore, for all $s \in \text{LCF}(x, y)$ we have $|s| \leq k - 1$. \square

B Auxiliary Results for the i.i.d. Model

B.1 v is well-defined

Statement B.1.1. The function v is well-defined (see 3.4.1).

Proof. Let $r \in (0, 1)$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}}$. The denominator of v , that is $\ln(r)$, is negative. The numerator of v , that is $\ln(1/n + 1/m)$, is well-defined and negative. In fact, $1/n + 1/m > 0$ and $\ln(1/n + 1/m) \leq \ln(2/89) < \ln(1/e) = -1$. Therefore, $v(r, n, m) \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$. \square

B.2 $k \leq m$

Definition B.2.1. Let $r \in (0, 1)$. We define the function $f_r : \mathbb{R}_{>0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that $f_r(x) := \ln(x) + (x - 1)\ln(r)$, the value $x_r := -1/\ln(r)$ and the interval $I_r := [x_r, +\infty)$.

Statement B.2.2. For all $d \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma$ we have $\phi_d \in (0, 1)$.

Proof. Let $d \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma$. By definition of $\mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma$, we have $\phi_d \leq 0.95$. So, $\phi_d < 1$. By definition of d , we have $d(\sigma_i) \in [0, 1]$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, |\Sigma|\}$, and we also have $d(\sigma_1) + \dots + d(\sigma_{|\Sigma|}) = 1$. If there did not exist $i \in \{1, \dots, |\Sigma|\}$ such that $d(\sigma_i) > 0$, then $d(\sigma_1) + \dots + d(\sigma_{|\Sigma|}) = 1$ would be contradicted. Therefore, $\phi_d > 0$. \square

Statement B.2.3. Let $r \in (0, 1)$. The function f_r is strictly decreasing on I_r . Moreover, if $f_r(x_r) \geq 0$ then it has a unique zero in I_r .

Proof. Let $r \in (0, 1)$. Since f_r is a sum of functions that are continuous and differentiable on $\mathbb{R}_{>0}$, it is continuous and differentiable on its domain. Specifically, $f_r'(x) = 1/x + \ln(r)$. The function f_r' is not defined on $(-\infty, 0]$, positive on $(0, x_r)$, zero at x_r and negative on $(x_r, +\infty)$. Consequently, f_r has a strict global maximum at x_r and is strictly decreasing on I_r . If $f_r(x_r) = 0$, then x_r is the only zero the function has in I_r . Suppose $f_r(x_r) > 0$, and let g_r denote the restriction of f_r to I_r . Since $\ln(r) < 0$, we have $\lim_{x \rightarrow +\infty} g_r(x) = -\infty$. By definition of limit, there exist $N \in (-\infty, 0)$ and $M \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for all $x > M$ we have $g_r(x) < N$. Thus, $g_r(x_s) < 0$ for some $x_s \in I_r$. By the intermediate value theorem, there exists $x' \in [x_r, x_s]$ such that $g_r(x') = 0$. Since g_r is strictly decreasing on I_r , we conclude that x' is the only zero of f_r on I_r . \square

Statement B.2.4. Let $r \in (0, 1)$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}}$. If $f_r(m) \leq 0$, then $\lceil v(r, n, m) \rceil \leq m$.

Proof. We make five observations.

First:

$$f_r(m) \leq 0 \quad \implies \quad -\ln(m) - (m-1)\ln(r) \geq 0$$

second:

$$-\ln(m) - (m-1)\ln(r) \geq 0 \quad \implies \quad \ln\left(\frac{1}{m}\right) \geq (m-1)\ln(r)$$

third:

$$\ln\left(\frac{1}{m}\right) \geq (m-1)\ln(r) \quad \implies \quad \ln\left(\frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{m}\right) \geq (m-1)\ln(r)$$

fourth:

$$\ln\left(\frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{m}\right) \geq (m-1)\ln(r) \quad \implies \quad v(r, n, m) \leq m-1$$

and fifth:

$$v(r, n, m) + 1 \leq m \implies \lceil v(r, n, m) \rceil \leq m$$

□

Statement B.2.5. Let $r \in (0, 1)$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}}$. For all $d \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma$ such that $\phi_d \leq r$, we have $\lceil v(\phi_d, n, m) \rceil \leq \lceil v(r, n, m) \rceil$.

Proof. Let $d \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma$ be such that $\phi_d \leq r$. As proved in B.2.2, we have $\phi_d \in (0, 1)$. Thus, $v(\phi_d, n, m)$ is well-defined. Since $\phi_d \leq r$, we have $\ln(\phi_d) \leq \ln(r)$. Dividing each side by $\ln(\phi_d) \ln(r)$, which is positive, yields $1/\ln(r) \leq 1/\ln(\phi_d)$. Multiplying each side by $\ln(1/n+1/m)$, which is negative as shown in the proof of B.1, yields $\ln(1/n+1/m)/\ln(r) \geq \ln(1/n+1/m)/\ln(\phi_d)$. That is, $v(\phi_d, n, m) \leq v(r, n, m)$. Therefore, as the ceiling function is non-decreasing on \mathbb{R} , we conclude that $\lceil v(\phi_d, n, m) \rceil \leq \lceil v(r, n, m) \rceil$.

□

Statement B.2.6. Let $r \in (0, 1)$, $d \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}}$. Suppose that $\phi_d \leq r$ and $f_r(x_r) \geq 0$. Let x' denote the unique zero of f_r in I_r (see B.2.3). If $m \geq x'$, then $\lceil v(\phi_d, n, m) \rceil \leq m$.

Proof.

By B.2.3:

$$m \geq x' \implies f_r(m) \leq 0$$

By B.2.4:

$$f_r(m) \leq 0 \implies \lceil v(r, n, m) \rceil \leq m$$

By B.2.5:

$$\lceil v(\phi_d, n, m) \rceil \leq \lceil v(r, n, m) \rceil$$

Therefore: if $m \geq x'$, then $\lceil v(\phi_d, n, m) \rceil \leq m$.

□

Statement B.2.7. Let $d \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}}$. We have $\lceil v(\phi_d, n, m) \rceil \leq m$.

Numerical Verification. Let $r := 0.95$. Suppose that $f_r(x_r) \geq 0$, and let x' denote the unique zero of f_r in $[x_r, +\infty)$ (see B.2.3). As we know by B.2.6: if $\phi_d \leq r$ and $m \geq x'$, then $\lceil v(\phi_d, n, m) \rceil \leq m$. A numerical calculation¹² yields $f_r(x_r) \approx 2.0215$, supporting the assumption that $f_r(x_r) \geq 0$. Continuing by numerically solving the equation $f_r(x) = 0$, we find the zeroes 1 and 88.3709. Since x_r approximates to 19.4957, we assume $x' \approx 88.3709$. To this end, note that $f_r(88.3709) \approx 1.4353 \cdot 10^{-6}$. The conditions $\phi_d \leq r$ and $m \geq x'$ are met, since $d \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{thr}}^\Sigma$ implies $\phi_d \leq 0.95$ and $m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq \text{thr}}$ implies $m \geq 89$. Therefore, we conclude that $\lceil v(\phi_d, n, m) \rceil \leq m$.

□

B.3 Probability of two k -grams being equal

Statement B.3.1. Let $d \in \mathcal{D}^\Sigma$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. Moreover, let $X \in \Sigma^n$ and $Y \in \Sigma^m$. For all $(i, j) \in \{1, \dots, n\} \times \{1, \dots, m\}$, the probability $\mathbb{P}(X[i] = Y[j])$ equals ϕ_d .

Proof. The event $\cup_{t=1}^z \{Y[j] = \sigma_t\}$ coincides with the sample space. Consequently, $\mathbb{P}(X[i] = Y[j])$ can be rewritten as:

$$\mathbb{P} \left((X[i] = Y[j]) \cap \bigcup_{t=1}^{|\Sigma|} Y[j] = \sigma_t \right)$$

By the distributivity of intersection over union, it can be further rewritten as:

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\bigcup_{t=1}^{|\Sigma|} (X[i] = \sigma_t) \cap (Y[j] = \sigma_t) \right)$$

¹²Numerical calculations were performed using the Wolfram Alpha computational engine, which is available at <https://www.wolframalpha.com>. Values are rounded to 4 decimal places.

The union is between pairwise disjoint events, so the probability equals:

$$\sum_{t=1}^{|\Sigma|} \mathbb{P}((X[i] = \sigma_t) \cap (Y[j] = \sigma_t))$$

For each $t \in \{1, \dots, z\}$, the events $\{X[i] = \sigma_t\}$ and $\{Y[j] = \sigma_t\}$ are independent. Thus, the above is equal to:

$$\sum_{t=1}^{|\Sigma|} \mathbb{P}(X[i] = \sigma_t) \cdot \mathbb{P}(Y[j] = \sigma_t)$$

Finally, for each $t \in \{1, \dots, z\}$ we have $\mathbb{P}(X[i] = \sigma_t) = \mathbb{P}(Y[j] = \sigma_t) = d(\sigma_t)$. Therefore, we conclude:

$$\mathbb{P}(X[i] = Y[j]) = \sum_{t=1}^{|\Sigma|} d(\sigma_t)^2 = \phi_d$$

□

Statement B.3.2. Let $d \in \mathcal{D}^\Sigma$ and $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 1}$. Moreover, let $t \in \{1, \dots, \min(n, m)\}$. Finally, let $X \in \Sigma^n$ and $Y \in \Sigma^m$. For all $(i, j) \in \{1, \dots, n-t+1\} \times \{1, \dots, m-t+1\}$, we have $\mathbb{P}(X^{(t)}[i] = Y^{(t)}[j]) = \phi_d^t$.

Proof. The event $\{X^{(t)}[i] = Y^{(t)}[j]\}$ can be rewritten as:

$$\bigcap_{\ell=1}^t X[i+\ell-1] = Y[j+\ell-1]$$

This is an intersection of mutually independent events. That is, for all $\ell \in \{1, \dots, t\}$ and $L \subseteq \{1, \dots, t\} \setminus \{\ell\}$, we have:

$$\mathbb{P}\left(X[i+\ell-1] = Y[j+\ell-1] \mid \bigcap_{\ell' \in L} X[i+\ell'-1] = Y[j+\ell'-1]\right) = \mathbb{P}(X[i+\ell-1] = Y[j+\ell-1])$$

This follows by the i.i.d. assumption, and by the fact that each element of X and Y is involved, at most, in a single comparison. For all $\ell \in \{1, \dots, t\}$, we have that $\mathbb{P}(X[i+\ell-1] = Y[j+\ell-1])$ equals ϕ_d (see [B.3.1](#)). Therefore, by the chain rule:

$$\mathbb{P}(X^{(t)}[i] = Y^{(t)}[j]) = \prod_{\ell=1}^t \mathbb{P}(X[i+\ell-1] = Y[j+\ell-1]) = \phi_d^t$$

□

References

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